

THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL NETWORK SITE USE INTENSITY DURING WORK HOURS ON THE EMPLOYEES' JOB PERFORMANCE

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Introduction

The recent innovations in Informational and Communication Technology (ICT) have created various opportunities to interact, link, and network with geographically dispersed working-age people. Applications of the Web 2.0 technology wave such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube, and WhatsApp have become popular around the globe as social media networks for sharing and obtaining information. Despite the facilities and technical support to work, the performance of employees gets high attention in workplaces (Kishokumar, 2016). Whether the employees get the right benefit from technological innovations in telecommunication, particularly social networks, during their work hours has become an important research topic.

The performance of an employee in a Job is defined in many ways, yet could generally be identified as "behaviours or actions that are relevant to the goals of the organization" (McCloy, Campbell, and Cudeck, 1994). The way to increase employee job performance is a long-standing and vital question for researchers and organizations as technology is considered to disrupt many job roles around the world. When it comes to the use of technology during work hours, Warnakula and Manickam (2011) revealed that most employees in Sri Lanka have access to social networking sites throughout their working hours. As a result, there is much discussion among academics and business practitioners over the benefit of organizational members using social networking during working hours.

Some studies indicate that the employee's usage of social networking sites during work hours is a waste of time (Nucleus, 2009; Rooksby, et al., 2009), while others say it improves job performance (Tulu, 2017; Moqbel, 2013). According to a survey by Robert Half Technology (2009), more than half of US companies block access to social networking sites to prevent employees from wasting time. However, according to Tulu (2017), preventing employees from using social networking sites is not viable for organizations because it would reduce employee productivity and performance. According to Baker (cited in Niranjana, 2018), using social networking sites can lead to role conflicts, negatively impacting work-related attitudes, including job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

On the other hand, anecdotal evidence suggests that social networking sites used by organizational members can improve organizational commitment (Leidner, Koch, and Gonzalez, 2010). However, the existing literature still does not provide enough evidence to prove that the use of social networking sites affects employees' job performance. (Moqbel, 2013). Furthermore, previous studies have not examined the impact of social network site use intensity on job performance as mediated by job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and knowledge sharing in the Sri Lanka context. Therefore, this research study expected to identify the factors influencing employees' job performance while using social network sites during work hours and the impact of social network site use intensity on employees' job performance.

Methodology

A comprehensive literature review was conducted and identified factors influencing the job performance of employees while using social network sites during work hours to achieve the research objectives. A conceptual model (Figure 1) was developed considering the constructs and relationships identified by Moqbel and Aftab (2015) and Min (2017) concerning the use of social network site use intensity, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and knowledge sharing (Cui, et al., 2019; Cao et al., 2012) on job performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

This research study used a deductive approach in quantitative research methodology to achieve the research objectives. All the constructs in the model were operationalized and identified eight hypotheses considering the relationships between the constructs in the conceptual model.

A questionnaire with close-ended seven-category Likert scale questions to measure all the constructs was developed considering the question items from previous research. Sales representatives in the age category between 18 and 40 (Millennials/Gen Y and post-millennials/Gen Z) were selected for the study. Sales representatives were used since the use of SNS is an independent choice for them as they do not have any external pressure to control SNS use during work hours. Additionally, they have defined targets and areas that they must cover within a specific timeframe; thus, their job performance could be measured easily. Millennials and post-millennials were selected as they are more conversant with technology, and the use of SNS has become a part of their life.

The expected sample size was calculated using Daniel Sopher's structural equation modelling sample size calculation and found that 150 valid responses were adequate to test the conceptual model. Accordingly, the questionnaire was distributed through online and offline modes to

respondents based on their preferred language Sinhala or English medium. The online questionnaire survey was conducted through Facebook and social media, and hard copies of the questionnaire were distributed among sales representatives with the support of shop owners around the country. The collected data were analyzed descriptively, and the conceptual model was tested through a Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique using the SmartPLS Professional version.

Results and Discussions

Through the data collection, 185 responses were collected, out of which 153 responses were identified as valid after removing the unengaged responses, missing values and responses not in the expected age range. Of the respondents, 92.8% (n=142) were males, and two-thirds of respondents were below 30 years of age. Based on the collected data, 82.2% (n=135) of respondents reported having more than two years of experience, and 82.4% (n=126) of respondents revealed that they are using SNS multiple times per day. However, the descriptive analysis of SNS use intensity questionnaire survey data revealed that the mean value of responses was 3.94, which is below the mid-point and high positive standard deviation. Thus, it's a sign that though they used SNS multiple times per day, the average use of SNS during work hours is low, and the use intensity varies from person to person.

For the model testing, all the constructs in the model were tested for reliability and validity. The Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and AVE (Average Variance Extracted) values were tested and found well above the threshold values proposed by Hair et. al (2014). In this study, internal Consistency Reliability is established because the composite reliability values range and Cronbach's Alpha values range are above acceptable values (0.7 or above). Convergent validity was also satisfied because all questionnaire items factor loading above 0.7 threshold values were selected, and the AVE value of all the variables was greater than 0.5

value. Since all the diagonal values were higher than other related values, the constructs show acceptable discriminant validity.

The model testing findings revealed that five out of eight hypotheses were supported under the 95% confidence level (Table 1). Social network site use intensity did not show a significant influence on job Performance (P=0.729). However, Social network site use intensity had shown a significant impact on job satisfaction (P=0.016), Organizational commitment (0.007), and knowledge sharing(P=0.000). Further, job satisfaction had a significant positive relationship with job performance (P=0.003) and organizational commitment (P=0.000). Even so, organizational commitment did not show a substantial impact on job performance (P=0.065). Unlike the earlier findings (DiMicco et al., 2014; Min 2017), knowledge sharing did not show a significant positive impact on the job performance of employees (P=0.923). According to Riege (cited in Ismail and Yusof, 2010) stated that individuals are hindered from sharing knowledge because of seventeen factors. Some of these factors include lack of awareness; fear that sharing may put at risk job security; lack of time to share knowledge; application of strong hierarchy, position-based status, and formal power; differences in levels of experience; lack of interaction; poor verbal/written communication and interpersonal skills; the difference in individuals age; the difference in individuals gender; lack of social network; differences of education levels; lack of trust in people because they mishandle knowledge or take unjust credit for it; lack of trust in the accuracy and credibility of knowledge due to the source; and differences in national culture or ethnic background along with values and beliefs associated with it.

Table 1: Significance testing results of the conceptual model

Hypotheses	Relationship	Path Coefficient	t Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Result
H1	SNSUI -> PERF	-0.028	0.347*	0.729	Not Supported
H2	SNSUI -> JS	0.184	2.412*	0.016	Supported
H3	JS -> PERF	0.361	2.946*	0.003	Supported

H4	JS -> OC	0.672	12.914*	0	Supported
H5	OC -> PERF	0.192	1.849*	0.065	Not Supported
H6	SNSUI -> OC	0.162	2.709*	0.007	Supported
H7	SNSUI -> KS	0.562	11.083*	0	Supported
H8	KS -> PERF	-0.009	0.096*	0.923	Not Supported

Note: ***p<0.01 **p<0.05

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to explore the use of social network sites by organizational members and their effect on job satisfaction, organizational commitment, knowledge sharing and job performance. The main objectives of this study were to identify the factors influencing employees' job performance while using SNS during work hours and to identify the relationship between employees' SNS use intensity during work hours and their job performance. The study revealed that, though social network site use intensity does not directly affect job performance, it could increase job performance through the intermediating variable of job satisfaction. However, knowledge sharing didn't show a significant association with job performance. Nevertheless, social network site use intensity could increase knowledge sharing and organizational commitment of employees, while job satisfaction could enhance employees' organizational commitment.

One of the key findings was that the majority of the respondents use social network sites multiple times a day, even though they do not show greater intensity in using social networks during work hours. Paying employees for a few minutes of work time spent on SNS does not appear to result in a financial loss. Nonetheless, it would improve employee productivity by increasing job satisfaction. Therefore, it is recommended that organizations should implement necessary policies to achieve maximum benefits from using social networks. This study demonstrates that SNS usage can enhance job satisfaction, knowledge sharing and organizational commitment.

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